

Selective Microgram Detection of Iron(III) on Ion Exchange Resin Beads

SYED A. NABI*, AHSAN R. SIDDIQUI, M. ATHAR
and
N. AHMAD

Department of Chemistry, Aligarh Muslim University,
Aligarh-202 001

Manuscript received 6 October 1980, accepted 21 July 1982

THE analytical importance of resin beads for the detection of inorganic and organic compounds have been well established¹⁻³. The advantage of using resin spot test over other detection techniques lies in the fact that it not only increases the sensitivity but also enhances the selectivity. Though a number of methods for the detection of iron(III) are available in the literature⁴⁻⁶, these are either insensitive or suffer from interferences of a large number of cations specially with Fe(II) and anions. We describe in this paper a sensitive and selective method for the detection of iron(III) on resin beads in microgram of the sample.

Experimental

Reagents : All the reagents used were of analytical grade.

Test solutions : Solutions of $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ (0.001 M) and anisaldimine antipyrine (0.5%) were prepared in distilled alcohol.

Resin : Dowex 50 W $\times$ 8 (20-30 mesh) in H^+ form was used after regeneration and washing with demineralized water. The beads were soaked on a filter paper and used for the detection.

Procedure : 5-10 beads of ion-exchange resin in H^+ form were taken in a spot plate. To this one drop of anisaldimine antipyrine solution was added. Then 0.1 ml of 0.001 M ferric nitrate (containing 5.6 μg of Fe) was added. The pH was maintained around 6. The beads turned pink after 2 min. The colour of the beads was compared by a simultaneous test in the absence of iron. With the successive increment in the iron content in the solution, the colour of the beads changes from pink to violet. The lower limit of the detection for iron(III) was found to be 1.12 μg .

Interferences : To show the analytical importance of the test, the detection of iron(III) (1.12 μg) was also performed in the presence of a large number of cations and anions using the above procedure. The limit of tolerance for each ion is given in Table 1.

The result of the above study reveals that iron in a sample can be successfully detected upto a limit of 1.12 μg using strong exchange resin in the H^+ form in the presence of anisaldimine antipyrine as reagent. The procedure is simple and less time consuming. The advantage of using the ion exchange beads as a detection medium is that it

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF FOREIGN IONS IN THE
DETECTION OF Fe(III); Fe(III) = 1.12 μg .

Sl. No.	Foreign ions	Limit of tolerance (μg)
1.	VO_2^+	500
2.	Cr^{3+}	500
3.	Co^{2+}	500
4.	Ni^{2+}	500
5.	Cu^{2+}	500
6.	Zn^{2+}	500
7.	Zr^{4+}	500
8.	Sn^{4+}	500
9.	Bi^{3+}	500
10.	Th^{4+}	500
11.	Ce^{3+}	500
12.	Pt^{4+}	500
13.	UO_2^{2+}	1000
14.	Na^+	1000
15.	K^+	1000
16.	Ca^{2+}	1000
17.	Mg^{2+}	1000
18.	Ba^{2+}	1000
19.	Sr^{2+}	1000
20.	Ib^{2+}	1000
21.	Al^{3+}	10.0
22.	Cd^{2+}	1000
23.	Li^{+}	1000
24.	La^{3+}	1000
25.	Hg^{2+}	1000
26.	Ag^+	1000
27.	Y^{3+}	250
28.	Acetate	250
29.	Molybdate	250
30.	Tungstate	1000
31.	Phosphate	1000
32.	Bromate	1000
33.	Iodate	1000
34.	Chlorate	1000
35.	Sulphate	1000
36.	Chloride	1000
37.	Bromide	1000
38.	Iodide	1000
39.	Chromate	1000
40.	Vanadate	1000
41.	Fe(II)	2000

retains the colour for a fairly long time after the test is performed. The colour starts disappearing at once when the same test is performed in the absence of beads. An additional advantage of this procedure is that it distinguishes between Fe(III) and Fe(II) as in the latter case the test gives negative results.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Professor W. Rahman, Head, Department of Chemistry, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh, for facilities and C.S.I.R., New Delhi for financial assistance to one of them (A. R. S.).

References

1. M. FUJIMOTO, *Chemist-Analyst.*, 1960, **49**, 4.
2. A. TSUJI, *Nippon Kagaku Zasshi*, 1963, **84**, 919.
3. J. H. YOH, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, **54**, 4189.
4. M. FUJIMOTO, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1956, **29**, 276.
5. V. ARMEANU, D. GAMBOLI and O. IANCU, *Anal. Abstract.*, 1960, **7**, 999.
6. E. SCHWIMMER, *Acta Chim. Acad. Sci. Hung.*, 1958, **14**, 311.